

PROCESSES OF ENGAGING YOUNG CHILDREN TO LEARN ENGLISH

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Abstract:

Methods that attract young children learn English. This article provides information on the types of activities in the form of games of that are currently used to teach English to young children. It contains information about the psychological characteristics of children of this age.

Key words: perceptive, read, listen and writing skills, psychological task, first alarm system, game, interval, thinking, language

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It is possible to take into account the psychological characteristics of students in small in order to ensure the effectiveness of English language training. In children of this age, visual-motor memory plays a more significant role than logical memory due to the dominance of the first alarm system. This younger people visual image thinking-the type of thinking based on directly perceived image of objects and intentions prevails. Pupils understanding is mainly based on what they have seen. Based on the features of memory and thinking of elementary school pupils, it is permissible to pay more attention to exhibitions in teaching English. Visual educational tools play an important role in developing children's supposing and memory. Then increasing children's psychological activity reduces fatigue and increases their interest in English.

On the one hand, it ensures the selection of material as visual aids, on the other hand, their mastery, and on the third hand, the practical application of the materials being organized.

A.Kuvshinkin offers several methods for teaching the alphabet. Along with the graphics of the English language, the graphophone simplifies the way of teaching similarities and helps children learn the language.

Game-this is the main energies of children in preschool and elementary school. Game plays an important grand in learning any other languages. In the theory of linguistics, a game is nothing more than an exercise.

E.U. Negvetiskaya said that the solution of communicative issues in the lesson should be formed around the first language and the language being taught. For example, in the distribution of roles or in explaining the rules. Language skills and communicative competence of students play a key role in introducing children to the educational process through games. The use of communicative and role-playing games has a good effect in teaching English for young children. For instance;

Famous person.

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Each pupil chooses a famous person and tells another child without saying his name, and the others ask him questions.

- Are you a male or female?
- How do you go about things?
- Which color are your eyes?

The task of “famous” is to give vague answers to questions so that they do not find out quickly. If the pupils find the answers correctly, the teacher and the game and announces the winner. At the end, you can ask the conducting questions.

- Did you find it challenging to guess?
- How quickly were you able to guess the name?

The use of toys has a good effect in teaching the behavior culture of pupils. I think, children of toys and name them. Please? Give me at the toy shop “What is your name?” It is easy to attract children`s attention through toys in such conversations with outside people.

Children of the first and second grades cannot concentrate their thoughts, but the pupils of the 3-4 grades can maintain their attention during the lessons, children should use a variety of exercises. For example, it is necessary to use mental or physical exercises. We can see it in the exercise “The wind is blowing”. In the game, all participants sit on chairs in a round. The person standing in the center of the circle is considered the leader. The leader says a strong wind is blowing in the direction of. Then to leader says the sign that everyone likes. For instance; The leader tells someone the color of somebody clothes. Whoever has these signs, they stand up. The participant who has not enough space becomes the leader. Neighboring places cannot be occupied. Let`s try another exercise. It is called the “Vegetable Cart” exercise: Everyone should have a chair except the manager. According to the pre-planned list, the manager names the vegetable according to each participant. In this game, at least 3 people must name one vegetable. The leader says the name of the vegetable, and participants who get the name of this vegetable change their places. If the leader leaves one of the pupils in place at this time, the pupil who is out of place becomes the leader. If the host shouts “Vegetable Cart” all players switch places. According to the research results, appropriate and rational use of the above – mentioned activities and mentally stimulating exercises increases the activity of pupils` mental abilities and acceptance of new knowledge. It is advisable to use such exercises at the beginning of the lesson, every 20 minutes, because of these exercises increase the activity of children.

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